

Beneficiary	REPORTED			Total Somme de Total costs	Total Somme de Max EU contribution	Total Somme de Organisation contribution
	Somme de Total costs	Somme de Max EU contribution	Somme de Organisation contribution			
P10-FLI	51,627.20	22,715.97	28,911.23	51,627.20	22,715.97	28,911.23
Y3 (2020)	51627.2	22715.97	28911.23	51627.2	22715.97	28911.23
P14-UT	130,040.09	57,217.64	72,822.45	130,040.09	57,217.64	72,822.45
Y3 (2020)	130040.09	57217.64	72822.45	130040.09	57217.64	72822.45
P17-UCM	106,221.56	46,737.49	59,484.07	106,221.56	46,737.49	59,484.07
Y3 (2020)	106221.56	46737.49	59484.07	106221.56	46737.49	59484.07
P23-UoS	55,453.01	24,399.32	31,053.69	55,453.01	24,399.32	31,053.69
Y3 (2020)	55453.01	24399.32	31053.69	55453.01	24399.32	31053.69
P25-NUIG	227,195.21	99,965.89	127,229.32	227,195.21	99,965.89	127,229.32
Y3 (2020)	227195.21	99965.89	127229.32	227195.21	99965.89	127229.32
P36-INSA	73,885.76	32,509.73	41,376.03	73,885.76	32,509.73	41,376.03
Y3 (2020)	73885.76	32509.73	41376.03	73885.76	32509.73	41376.03
TOTAL	644,422.83	283,546.04	360,876.79	644,422.83	283,546.04	360,876.79